

The Effect of Informativeness, Photo Colour, Visual Aesthetic, and Social Presence towards Customer Purchase Intention on Glory of fats Instagram

Nico Salim, Ronald & Amelia

Abstract

In the era of social media that has been grow rapidly in the past few years bring a huge impact for everyone and businesses. Businesses must adapt in the changing method of promoting their brand and product through social media to increase Customer Purchase Intention by posting a photo content on their social media account. Product photo plays an important role to increase customer purchase intention nowadays, because it could help the customers to create visualization about the actual product. The purpose of this research study is to find out the effect of Informativeness, Photo Colour, Visual Aesthetic, and Social Presence towards Customer Purchase Intention. The data was being collected by distributing a questionnaire to 100 respondents which consist of male and female, ever visits Glory of Fats Instagram account, and ever purchase the products. The data being analyzed using Structural Equation Model (SEM) and with AMOS 22.0 software. The empirical findings indicated that there is a positive significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention variables are Informativeness (H1) with the C.R. Value of 4,795; Photo Colour (H2) with the C.R. Value of 4,343; Visual Aesthetic (H3) with the C.R. Value of 4,599; Social Presence (H4) with the C.R. Value of 4,568.

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About Author (s)

Nico Salim (corresponding author), Economic and Business School, Magister of Management, Pelita Harapan University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Dr. Ronald, S.T., M.M., CSMA, CDM, PMA, Pelita Harapan University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Dr. Amelia, S.E., RFP-I. M.M., CSMA, Pelita Harapan University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Introduction

The era of social media has been changed a lot in the past few years, social media could bring a huge impact for everyone. Everyone could easily participate in social media to share an information about something valuable or entertaining and they also could promote a brand through social media (Simplilearn, 2022). Social media refers to explain about the use of computer-based technology in order to facilitate their users to share ideas, information to a community in the form of photo, videos, or text via websites or applications (Dollarhide, 2021). Social media is a digital tool that allows anyone to create and share any content to the public instantly without any hesitation due to the wide range of social media options (Hudson, 2020). The characteristics of social media according to (Lucas, 2022), firstly, social media could be easily accessible everyone and it's also become a meeting point for the internet geek. Secondly, the biggest percentage of social media users come from the young generation, teenagers, and middle aged. Thirdly, social media provides a direct access to client without any third-party interruptions. Lastly, advertising through social media could save a lot of cost being compared with another conventional way of advertising method. In other hand, there are so many social media platforms that could be used as a marketing tools, such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and etc. People nowadays using social media platform to do business, because by using social media they could easily grow their business without having an issue about a limited advertising budget (Dowd, 2021). Social media plays an important role in shopping situation right now and will keep growing as a platform for company to commercialize their products and to maintain their relationship with the customers (Blood-Rojas, 2017). Instagram is an online photo-sharing platform that allows their users to edit and upload their photo or video through mobile apps that have been acquired by Facebook since 2012 (Holak & McLaughlin, 2017). Instagram was created by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger in 2010, which they are classmates at Stanford University (Harrison, 2020). Instagram users have been growing drastically from time to time, in 2022 total of Instagram users in Indonesia around 104 million of active users. Nowadays, many brands using Instagram to market their product by providing a visual content. Brands should use an attractive visual content to attract and communicate with their audience effectively (Goodman, 2021). Because human brains tend to remember more visual things longer rather than just only text content, visual also has been prove to improve understanding and motivation to take an action while consuming the content (Sheikh, 2020). Visual content such as a product photo plays an important role in selling product through social media. Product photo could help the brands to create an impression to their target customers, product photo also could increase the product description which could easily attract buyers to purchase the product (Malvika, 2015). However, the image quality also plays an important role because buyers could closely check the product through the images by zooming and it could give them the perception of the product itself (Hiils, 2022). In the other hand, by having a professional product photo, it will help to convinced the customers that the brands care for what their wants & needs which could make their customers become a loyal customer and could repeatedly re-purchase the product (C-Reel, 2022). Customers also will be faced by a lot of choices that are available online, so brands have to provide an eye-catching product photo with an information on it to capture the sales quickly (Newell, 2021). Product photo that are being provided

Literature Review

Customer Purchase Intention

According to (Kotler, Keller, Goodman, & Hansen, 2016), Customer purchase intention is a form of customer behaviour that wish to purchase or choose a product based on their experience, use and a desire of a product. Customer Purchase Intention is a tendency of customer to purchase a brand and generally based on purchase motive compatibility towards the attributes or the characteristic of the brand (Stevina & Brahmana, 2016). According to Vranesevic and

Stanandccaronec in (Widjanarko & Harsono, 2019), Customer purchase intention is an individual intention to buy a specific brand that they have been selected and wished to purchase after doing research. Customer purchase intention is a type of decision making that has been made for a reason why the customer tend to buy the product from certain brands (Shah, et al., 2012), Customer purchase intention is a consumer tendency to purchase a product from a brand or an action that are related to buying decision that are already being measured by the opportunity of consumer to purchase (Muthohar & Triatmaja, 2013). Customer purchase intention is a form of customer desire to purchase the product because they know about the functionality of the product itself (Madahi & Sukati, 2012). According to (Raza, Ahad, Shafqat, Aurangzaib, & Rizwan, 2014), Customer purchase intention is a process where consumers do a research about their knowledge of the product, comparing the product with another similar product, and make a decision about the product that they are going to purchase.

Informativeness

Informativeness is how good brands could provide an information to help their customer in decision making before they purchase the product (Alalwan, 2018). According to (Alalwan, 2018), in their research stated that informativeness significantly influences towards customer purchase intention. Which indicate that customers will likely to purchase the product when they got a bunch of information that are related to the product. Therefore, we tested the following hypothesis:

H1: Informativeness has a significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention.

Photo Colour

Photo colour is how the colour being organized and process to produce an interesting colour arrangement with an artistic value that can be seen or enjoy visually. Photo colour is an important aspect in visual because each colour that being processed has a different characteristic and meaning itself (Hasian & Putri, 2021). According to (Andika, 2018), in their research stated that photo color significantly influence towards customer purchase intention. Which indicate that color plays an important role in purchase intention while having a good color combination could easily attract buyers. Therefore, we tested the following hypothesis:

H2: Photo Colour has a significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention.

Visual Aesthetic

Visual aesthetic is how aesthetic style that being embed through visualization of the presenter and how others assuming it to be visually attractive and aesthetically appealing (Yang, Tang, Zhang, & Yang Ruo, 2021). According to (Puspahati, Gunawan, & Sugihartanto, 2021), in their research stated that visual aesthetic significantly influences towards customer purchase intention. Which indicate that by providing an attractive photo could influence customer to purchase. Therefore, we tested the following hypothesis:

H3: Visual Aesthetic has a significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention.

Social Presence

Social presence is an object media where allows the viewers to experience the product through photo as being present psychologically (Li, Wang, & Chen, 2014). According to (Li, Wang, & Chen, 2014), in their research stated that social presence significantly influences towards customer purchase intention. Which indicate that showing images with a human face could increase the customer desire to purchase the product. Therefore, we tested the following hypothesis:

H4: Social Presence has a significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention.

Research Issue and Methodology

In this research, the data analysis method that are being used in this research study is a quantitative data method by using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) and being process by using AMOS 22.0 software. The data was being collected by distributing questionnaire to 100 respondents which consist of male and female, with an age range of 18 - 60 years old, ever visits Glory of Fats Instagram account, and ever purchase the product of Glory of Fats. The sampling technique that being used is non-probability sampling by spreading questionnaires as a data collection tools, and also the researcher using snowball sampling technique to collect the data of the respondents to obtain a precise data result. The research model could be seen as follow:

Figure 3-1. Research Model

Source: Xin Li, Mengyue Wang, Yubo Chen (2014)

Finding and Discussion

Findings

This research study is using Structural Equation Model (SEM) in analysing the variables and also using AMOS 22.0 software to process and calculate to obtain the answer of the problem of this research. After the questionnaires have been filled out and being collected back, and the next step should be conducted is the descriptive statistic-analysis.

Figure 4-1. Age of Respondent Chart

Source: Author

In figure 4-1, it shows the majority of the respondent with the age range of ≤ 20 years old (45%) and being followed with the age range of 21-25 years old (42%), lastly with the age range of 26-30 years old (13%).

Figure 4-2. Gender of Respondent Chart
Source: Author

In figure 4-2, it shows the majority of the respondent are Female with 64 Respondent (64%) and male respondent with 36 respondents (36%).

Figure 4-3. Domicile of Respondent Chart
Source: Author

In figure 4-3, it shows the majority of the respondent are based on Medan (100%).

Table 4.1: Respondent by Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18	14.0	14.0	14.0
	19	14.0	14.0	28.0
	20	17.0	17.0	45.0
	21	11.0	11.0	56.0
	22	6.0	6.0	62.0
	23	5.0	5.0	67.0
	24	11.0	11.0	78.0
	25	9.0	9.0	87.0
	26	11.0	11.0	98.0
	27	1.0	1.0	99.0
	28	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author

Table 4-1 shows that the majority of respondents (45%) are between the ages of 18 until 20 years old, followed by those between 21 until 25 years old (42%), and those between 26 until 30 years old (13%).

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistic

Variable	Indicator	Description	Descriptive Statistic	
			Mean	SD
<i>Informativeness (X1)</i>	I-1	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram able to show the details of the product well.	3,63	1,02
	I-2	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram that are being displayed are the actual size.	3,53	1,01
	I-3	I feel that product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram are able to provide a proper the information that are being needed.	3,70	0,97
<i>Photo Colour (X2)</i>	PC-1	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram that are being displayed have a warm colour mood as needed.	3,78	1,06
	PC-2	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram that are being displayed have a cool colour mood as needed.	3,60	0,89
	PC-3	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram that are being displayed are the bright colour choices.	3,56	1,04
	PC-4	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram that are being displayed are the pop-ups colours.	3,53	1,01
	PC-5	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram that are being displayed a bright photos.	3,35	1,05
<i>Visual Aesthetic (X3)</i>	VA-1	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram have sharp photos.	3,75	1,03
	VA-2	I feel that the product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram have an interesting photo property decoration.	3,54	1,04
	VA-3	I feel that product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram always have a good background.	3,70	1,19
<i>Social Presence (X4)</i>	SP-1	I feel that product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram will be more attractive if they are supported by the suitable model.	3,64	0,98
	SP-2	I feel that product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram would be more interesting if they used mannequins as product samples.	3,78	1,02
	SP-3	I feel that product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram will be more interesting if the model shown the full body.	3,91	0,95
<i>Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)</i>	PI-1	I will purchase the Glory of Fats products that are being advertised on the Instagram again.	2,99	1,47
	PI-2	I will recommend Glory of Fats products to others.	3,12	1,50
	PI-3	I will always look for an information about Glory of Fats products through their Instagram.	3,04	1,49

Source: Author

Based on the results on the table 4-2 above, all of the variable's indicators with a standard deviation value is below 2.0 which shows that the respondent responses are homogeneous. The highest mean average is 3,91 with the indicator of SP-3 with a statement *I feel that product photos on Glory of Fats Instagram will be more interesting if the model shown the full body*, which means the respondent agree with the statement. The indicator of PI-2 has the highest standard deviation value with 1,50 with a statement *I will recommend Glory of Fats products to others*, it

indicates that the respondent responses are the least homogenous being compared with others.

Construct Validity

Factor loading for CFA Exogenous Construct value should be bigger than 0.50 to be considered as valid in forming the construct validity and to be used to build a model.

Figure 4-4 CFA Exogenous Construct

Source: Author

Table 4-3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Exogeneous Construct

Construct	Indicator	Factor Loading	Critical Value	Result
Informativeness (X1)	I-1	0,706	≥ 0,50	Valid
	I-2	0,768	≥ 0,50	Valid
	I-3	0,771	≥ 0,50	Valid
Photo Colour (X2)	PC-1	0,794	≥ 0,50	Valid
	PC-2	0,693	≥ 0,50	Valid
	PC-3	0,675	≥ 0,50	Valid
	PC-4	0,785	≥ 0,50	Valid
	PC-5	0,707	≥ 0,50	Valid
Visual Aesthetic (X3)	VA-1	0,665	≥ 0,50	Valid
	VA-2	0,771	≥ 0,50	Valid
	VA-3	0,671	≥ 0,50	Valid

Social Presence (X4)	SP-1	0,833	≥ 0,50	Valid
	SP-2	0,876	≥ 0,50	Valid
	SP-3	0,736	≥ 0,50	Valid
Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)	PI-1	0,803	≥ 0,50	Valid
	PI-2	0,889	≥ 0,50	Valid
	PI-3	0,748	≥ 0,50	Valid

Source: Author

According to Table 4-3, each of the indicator in each exogenous construct (informativeness, photo colour, visual aesthetic, and social presence) has a factor loading value that is greater than 0.50, which indicates that these indicators can be used to build the models.

Reliability Test

Table 4-4 Construct Reliability

Variable	Construct Reliability	AVE	Result
Informativeness (X1)	0,793	0,561	Reliable
Photo Colour (X2)	0,852	0,536	Reliable
Visual Aesthetic (X3)	0,746	0,504	Reliable
Social Presence (X4)	0,857	0,668	Reliable
Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)	0,856	0,665	Reliable
Requirements	≥0,70	≥0,50	

Source: Author

Each of the construct has a construct reliability value that is bigger than 0.70 and an AVE value that is bigger than 0.50. It indicates that these construct of informativeness, photo colour, visual aesthetic, and social presence are reliable in expressing by these indicators.

Full Structural Equation Modelling

Figure 4-5 SEM Model Estimation Result

Source: Author

Table 4-5 SEM Conformity Index

Goodness Fit Criteria	Index Value	Critical Value	Result	
Absolute Fit Indices	Probability Chi-square	0,066	> 0,05	Good fit
	Cmin/DF	1,211	≤ 2,00	Good fit
	GFI	0,861	≥ 0,90	Marginal fit
	RMSEA	0,046	≤ 0,08	Good fit
Incremental Fit Indices	TLI	0,970	≥ 0,95	Good fit
	CFI	0,962	≥ 0,95	Good fit
Parsimony Fit Indices	AGFI	0,805	≥ 0,90	Marginal fit

Source: Author

According to the table 4-5 above, it shows that all of the model suitability criteria (good fit or marginal fit) were met, allowing the structural model to be accepted. A good fit means the model already has a good model fit, however a marginal fit means that the model conformance is within acceptable parameters.

Testing Structural Relationship

Table 4-6 Hypothesis Testing

Hip	Influence Between Variables	Std. Estimate	C.R.	P-Value
H1	Informativeness (X1) → Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)	0,478	4,795	0,000
H2	Photo Colour (X2) → Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)	0,319	4,343	0,000
H3	Visual Aesthetic (X3) → Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)	0,429	4,599	0,000
H4	Social Presence (X4) → Customer Purchase Intention (Y1)	0,362	4,568	0,000

Source: Author

Table 4-6 above shows that the C.R. value for the variables of Informativeness (H1), Photo Colour (H2), Visual Aesthetic (H3), and Social Presence (H4) is greater than 1.96. This means that the relationships between the variables are positively significant.

Discussion

Based on the finding results of this research study, Informativeness, Photo Colour, Visual Aesthetic, and Social Presence all shows a positive and significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention. The most influential variable on Customer Purchase Intention is Informativeness with a regression coefficient value of 0,478 and P-Value of 0,000. Which means that the more informative product photo on the Glory of Fats Instagram, it will increase the customer intention to purchase the product. This result study aligns with Alawan (2018) that stated that Informativeness significantly influences towards Customer Purchase Intention. Table 4-7 shows that I-3 is the most accurate indicator from the Informativeness variable with a lambda loading value of 0,771.

Table 4-7 Informativeness (I) Indicator

Variable	Indicator	Lambda Loading	Mean
Informativeness (X1)	I-1	0,706	3,63
	I-2	0,768	3,53
	I-3	0,771	3,70

Source: Author

The second most influential variable on Customer Purchase Intention is Visual Aesthetic with regression coefficient value of 0,429 and P-Value of 0,000. This result study aligns with Puspahati, Gunawan, & Sugihartanto (2021) that stated that Visual Aesthetic significantly influences towards Customer Purchase Intention. Table 4-8 shows that VA-2 is the most accurate indicator from the Visual Aesthetic variable with a lambda loading value of 0,771.

Table 4-8 Visual Aesthetic (VA) Indicator

Variable	Indicator	Lambda Loading	Mean
Visual Aesthetic (X3)	VA-1	0,665	3,75
	VA-2	0,771	3,54
	VA-3	0,671	3,70

Source: Author

The third most influential variable on Customer Purchase Intention is Social Presence with regression coefficient value of 0,362 and P-Value of 0,000. This result study aligns with Li, Wang, & Chen (2014) that stated that Social Presence significantly influences towards

Customer Purchase Intention. Table 4-9 shows that SP-2 is the most accurate indicator from the Social Presence variable with a lambda loading value of 0,876.

Table 4-9 Social Presence (SP) Indicator

Variable	Indicator	Lambda Loading	Mean
Social Presence (X4)	SP-1	0,833	3,64
	SP-2	0,876	3,78
	SP-3	0,736	3,91

Source: Author

The fourth most influential variable on Customer Purchase Intention is Photo Colour with regression coefficient value of 0,319 with P-Value of 0,000. This result study aligns with Andika (2018) that stated that Photo Colour significantly influences towards Customer Purchase Intention. Table 4-10 shows that PC-1 is the most accurate indicator from the Photo Colour variable with a lambda loading value of 0,794.

Table 4-10 Photo Colour (PC) Indicator

Variable	Indicator	Lambda Loading	Mean
Photo Colour (X2)	PC-1	0,794	3,78
	PC-2	0,693	3,60
	PC-3	0,675	3,56
	PC-4	0,785	3,53
	PC-5	0,707	3,35

Source: Author

Conclusion

This research study model was being developed in order to understand the effect between Informativeness (I), Photo Colour (PC), Visual Aesthetic (VA), and Social Presence (SP) towards Customer Purchase Intention (PI). From the research study that has been conducted, Informativeness, Visual Aesthetic, Social Presence, and Photo Colour both all of the variables have a positive and significant influence towards Customer Purchase Intention. As a result, the managerial implication will concentrate around the significant variables. First, for the Informativeness variables, it is being suggested that they could improve their product photo content by integrating product details such as ingredients, composition, and flavour. Furthermore, Glory of Fats also could provide the sizing measurement in the photo so the consumer understands how big or small the item is, and the client will not feel tricked if the actual item does not meet their expectations. Glory of Fats can also insert a funny facts or stories behind the culinary products they make, providing additional entertainment to customers. Second, for the Visual Aesthetic factors, it is suggested that they place a decoration on their product photo in accordance with the current world event. It was also suggested that Glory of Fats be able to produce a high-quality picture to show their professionalism in order to maintain Glory of Fats's level in the competitive market. Glory of Fats might provide a product photo with a different background in different settings, such as a park, garden, or beach, to generate a visualization and impression that can make the audience feel that the product is suitable to be taken anyplace. Third, for the Social Presence variables, it is being suggested that a group of family members could be used as a model on their product photo to produce fun and pleasant emotions that may create a positive impact on the audience. Glory of Fats could engage the audience by stimulating their imagination through animated text material, model audio and videos, and artificial intelligence. Glory of Fats is also being suggested that in order to keep up with current trends, they should create product imagery content that is relevant to continuing trends. Fourth, for the Photo Colour variables, it is being suggested that producing an appealing product photo by creating a pop-up color visualization on their product photo as how the

buyers will receive the product when they purchase it. Glory of Fats should pay attention to the color combination of the product photo in order to maintain and produce a positive emotion for the customers. Glory of Fats must also present a consistent color scheme on their Instagram account in order to establish and maintain a professional brand image in the market.

Suggestions For Further Study

This research study is examined the effect of Informativeness, Photo Colour, Visual Aesthetic, and Social Presence towards Customer Purchase Intention. It is required to do an additional research on the effect of Informativeness, Photo Colour, Visual Aesthetic, and Social Presence on different Instagram business account in various business industry. This could enable the researcher to compare different conclusions concerning the widespread adoption of the Informativeness, Photo Colour, Visual Aesthetic, and Social Presence in the era of social media. It is also being recommended to supplement the existing variables in this research study to increase the understanding of this factors. Brand Image, Habit, Design, etc., all are possible to become a new area for doing a research in the future.

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